

Use of long-term individual data on birds as a source of biodiversity information

NLBIF project report

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Project information

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Background

Long-term data on bird populations have been collected across the globe, ranging from population-level breeding data (e.g., number of breeding pairs per year) to individual-level data (e.g., fitness, behaviour, genetic information). These data are irreplaceable sources of knowledge on biodiversity, and of the evolutionary and ecological processes that shape it. Researchers working on breeding populations of individually marked birds have been working together in comparative studies for decades, but collaboration was often hindered by a lack of data findability, accessibility and standards. Bird ringing schemes in Europe have been organised and coordinated through EURING (du Feu *et al.* 2016), but a centralised community for long-term individual-based field studies only started with the establishment of SPI-Birds (Studies of Populations of Individual Birds) in 2019 (Culina *et al.* 2021).

SPI-Birds Network and Database (<https://spibirds.org>) makes research groups and their datasets visible, archives data, and facilitates data findability, sharing and comparative, cross-dataset analysis. For this purpose, SPI-Birds has been working extensively on creating a data standard agreed upon by the community that adheres to the FAIR principles (Wilkinson *et al.* 2016). Since its launch, SPI-Birds has been very successful, stimulating a large degree of community participation, hosting (meta)data collected by 123 studies, covering 225 populations of 38 species.

All metadata on the studies hosted by SPI-Birds are openly available through the SPI-Birds website. However, many of the datasets themselves are not unconditionally open access, largely because research groups wanted to retain ownership of their data when they join the SPI-Birds network. Yet, SPI-Birds has been contributing towards a cultural shift within the network; the number of data owners that are willing to make their data open is increasing.

Visibility and usability of the data hosted at SPI-Birds to communities not working on individually marked birds is still low. To increase findability of data and facilitate its use to external communities, we aimed to improve the alignment with existing metadata standards and make summary information available through GBIF. Hosting more than 100,000 datasets and spanning 142 countries/areas, GBIF serves a much larger audience than SPI-Birds. Also, in terms of types of users, GBIF and SPI-Birds vary; where SPI-Birds is mostly used by bird researchers with a focus on ecology and evolutionary biology, GBIF is used by a wide variety of biodiversity scientists.

Project objectives and deliverables

In this project we set out to increase the findability, visibility, and usability of datasets hosted at SPI-Birds to a wider research community, beyond the typical users in the SPI-

Birds network. We achieved this through two tasks: (1) standardisation of SPI-Birds' metadata following the Ecological Metadata Language (EML; Jones *et al.* 2019); (2) standardisation of SPI-Birds' summary data to Darwin Core and mobilisation to GBIF.

Metadata standardisation

To further strengthen SPI-Birds' contribution to the movement towards open and FAIR data, and increase data visibility to external users (i.e., users outside the SPI-Birds network), we adopted EML as our metadata standard for newly incoming datasets. We did this for several reasons. First, EML is a widely used standard in ecology and adjacent research fields. Second, EML is (1) compatible with other standards, (2) modular, in that it allows flexibility in describing one's metadata, and (3) community-oriented, in that it is continuously evolving to meet the needs of the community. These properties resonate well with the philosophy of SPI-Birds, where we also frequently reflect and adapt our data standard based on user experience. Third, EML is the metadata standard used by GBIF. Adopting EML as a metadata standard at SPI-Birds will make it easier to mobilise data in the future (see 'Reflection and outlook').

Working with metadata schema, its formats and terminologies is not straightforward for the average contributors (researchers) in the SPI-Birds network. Therefore, we have developed an online form (<https://eu.jotform.com/form/230361997667066>) to facilitate entering (and updating) the metadata for studies (done by data contributors). Further, this helps SPI-Birds data managers to standardise the metadata inputs before transforming it to EML.

Data standardisation and mobilisation

The second component of this project involved the creation of a SPI-Birds-to-Darwin-Core (SPI-Birds-DwC) pipeline. Specifically, we developed a pipeline (<https://github.com/SPI-Birds/darwincore>) that retrieves annual breeding pairs per species per year per study site from SPI-Birds formatted data (v1.1.0; https://github.com/SPI-Birds/documentation/blob/master/standard_protocol/SPI_Birds_Protocol_v1.1.0.pdf) and transforms that into a Darwin Core Archive consisting of a *dwc:Event* core and a *dwc:Occurrence* extension. This pipeline was created in R because this is the most used programming language in our field of research and the language we use to develop SPI-Birds data standardisation pipelines (<https://github.com/SPI-Birds/pipelines>).

Given the time frame of the project, the SPI-Birds-DwC pipeline was developed using the NIOO-managed studies at SPI-Birds as a test case. This dataset spans:

- 7 sites in the Netherlands where NIOO-KNAW have been conducting long-term research (i.e., Buunderkamp, Liesbos, Hoge Veluwe, Oosterhout, Vlieland, Warnsborn, Westerheide)
- 69 years (1955-2023)
- 8 unique bird species (*Parus major*, *Cyanistes caeruleus*, *Ficedula hypoleuca*, *Periparus ater*, *Sitta europaea*, *Passer montanus*, *Phoenicurus phoenicurus*, *Poecile palustris*)
- 1,350 records of annual breeding pairs per site, year, species

These data were successfully published to and registered at GBIF:

Visser ME, Culina A, Vriend SJG, Jantzen CC (2024)
 Breeding pair abundances derived from nestbox studies of the Netherlands Institute of Ecology (NIOO-KNAW).
 The Netherlands Institute of Ecology (NIOO-KNAW).
 Sampling event dataset <https://doi.org/10.15468/n3rm4u>.

Reflection and outlook

In addition to our achievements highlighted above, we had sought to develop an application programming interface (API), through which we could automate the sharing of SPI-Birds data with GBIF. We were unsuccessful in developing an API within the timeframe of the project because (1) data hosted at SPI-Birds are currently not in a formal database and, with that, not straightforwardly available through a single access point, and (2) we could not match our wishes for the API with the authentication and encryption requirements at the organisation (NIOO-KNAW).

However, in the time between finishing this project and producing the project report, SPI-Birds partners were successful in acquiring funding for a two-year project titled “FAIR Bird Research Data and Software (FAIRBiRDS): closing the research lifecycle in the long tail of science”. FAIRBiRDS (started in March 2024) is a collaboration between bird researchers involved in SPI-Birds and computer engineers experienced with providing FAIR data & software solutions in academic research. One of the main objectives of the project is the development of a formal data repository, in which data contributors can easily submit/update their metadata (in EML) as well as their data, and data users can easily query and request the standardised data (through REST APIs). FAIRBiRDS also provides a way to further advance the metadata form that we have developed in this project. A second main objective of the FAIRBiRDS project is expansion of the user base. We will use the easy-to-fill metadata form to expand SPI-Birds’ coverage to underrepresented geographic areas (e.g., South America or Africa), ecosystems (e.g., tropical forests) and species with different ecologies (e.g., cooperative or colonial

breeders). By the time FAIRBiRDS reaches its final phase (early 2026), we will re-evaluate the opportunity to link SPI-Birds to GBIF and share SPI-Birds-hosted data with GBIF, as we had originally aspired to do within the scope of this project.

References

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